

Online Data Supplement

Title: Exploring antiviral and anti-inflammatory effects of thiol drugs in COVID-19

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Materials and Methods

Inhibition of authentic SARS-CoV-2 infection

For the preliminary live virus infection experiment (Figure S4A-E), SARS-CoV-2 (Wuhan-1) of 1.2×10^4 TCID₅₀/ml was incubated with 2-fold serially diluted thiol-based drugs (0.4-6.25 mM for cysteamine and WR-1065, 6.25-100mM for Mesna and bucillamine) at 37°C for 2 hrs. Virus-drug mixtures were diluted 12-fold before addition to Vero E6 cell monolayer in 96-well-plate. For each drug concentration, virus-drug mixtures were added to 10 replicate wells at 100 µl per well. The final titer of virus added to cells was 1×10^3 TCID₅₀/ml (100 TCID₅₀ per 100 µl per well in 96-well-plate). After two hours of infection, virus-drug inoculum was replaced with fresh DMEM medium containing 1% FBS. Clear CPE developed after two days of incubation at 37°C with 5% CO₂. The experiment was repeated thrice. Wells with clear CPE were counted positive and percentage of positive wells for each concentration of tested drugs were plotted. The effect of thiol-based drugs on Vero E6 cells during the two hours of SARS-CoV-2 infection was evaluated by addition of 8.33 mM or 0.52 mM of each drug and 100 TCID₅₀ SARS-CoV-2 simultaneously to Vero E6 cell monolayer in 96-well-plate (Figure SF). These concentrations reflect highest concentration, post 12-fold dilution of drugs when virus/drug mix was incubated with the cells in the virus pre-treatment experiment. After two hours of infection, cells were washed and then cultured with fresh DMEM medium containing 1% FBS at 37°C with 5% CO₂. Clear CPE developed two days post infection.

Quantification of cell viability

For all cell viability experiments, the experimental protocol was the same as the main experiment except for the step of pseudovirus or authentic virus infection. For the cell viability measurement corresponding to the preliminary live virus experiment (Figure S4A-E), Vero E6 cells were incubated with different concentrations (0.03-8.3mM) of the drugs for 2 hours, followed by removal of the drugs and incubation of cells with culture medium containing 1% FBS for 2 days. These concentrations reflect the 12-fold dilution of drugs when virus/drug mix was incubated with the cells in the live virus infection setting. Post incubation, the plates and their contents were equilibrated at room temperature for 30 minutes before addition of equal volumes of CellTiter Glo2.0 reagent. Afterwards, the contents were mixed on a plate shaker to induce cell lysis. The plates were then incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes followed by measurement of luminescence using Biotek plate reader. Luciferase reads of control-treated cells was set as 100% and the relative viability of cells incubated in the presence of thiol-based drugs was calculated. The experiment was carried out thrice with 6 replicates in each for all the drug concentrations.

IC50 determination

IC50 values were determined using the non-linear regression fitting with a variable slope in GraphPad Prism (version 9.2).

Equation: log(inhibitor) vs normalized response with variable slope

Model: $Y=100/(1+10^{((\text{LogIC50}-X)*\text{HillSlope}))})$

Figure S1.

A

B

Figure S1. Effect of penicillamine and succimer on binding of SARS-CoV-2-RBD to ACE2. (A) Percent of binding in the presence of the penicillamine and succimer (n = 4 - 6). Without drug treatment, the binding was 100%, whereas treatment with the thiol-based drugs showed a decrease in the binding % relative to no drug control. The X axis is scaled to log₂. **(B)** Histograms denoting areas under the curve (AUC) analyses for binding studies in panel B, in which the AUC is the % binding of ACE2 to RBD in the presence of each drug. The reference AUC is determined from the % binding of ACE to RBD in the absence of drug. The dashed line represents 50% of reference AUC. Data are mean ± SEM.

Figure S2.

Figure S2. Schematic illustration of the strategies employed to assess thiol drugs as pseudovirus entry inhibitors. (A) Pseudovirus (PV) pretreatment: The SARS-2-PVs were pre-incubated with thiol-based drugs prior to transduction of the HEK293T-ACE2-TMPRSS2 cells. **(B) Cell pretreatment:** The HEK293T-ACE2-TMPRSS2 cells were exposed to thiol-based drugs before the cells were transduced with SARS-2-PV.

Figure S3.

Figure S3. Effect of pretreatment of HEK293T-ACE2-TMPRSS2 cells with thiol drugs on the entry of pseudoviruses (ancestral strain Wuhan-1) in the cells. Pseudovirus entry efficiency, quantified by luciferase activity, when the cells were exposed to drugs prior to transduction with untreated virus (as illustrated in Figure S2B), (n = 3). The effects of drugs on viability of HEK293T-ACE2-TMPRSS2 cells was quantified using Cell Titer Glo 2.0 (n=3). The drug doses reflect the 66-fold dilution of drugs when pseudovirus/drug mixture was incubated with cells in the pseudovirus pretreatment strategy. The X-axis are scaled to log10. Percentage changes are with respect to no drug control which is set as 100%. Data are mean \pm SD.

Figure S4

Figure S4. Effect of thiol drugs on authentic SARS-CoV-2 infection (Wuhan-1). (A to E) Cytopathic effects (CPE) quantified by visual inspection when virus is exposed to (A) carbocysteine (negative control) and thiol drugs (B) Mesna, (C) Bucillamine, (D) Cysteamine, (E) WR-1065 prior to infection in Vero E6 cells (n = 3). The effects of drugs on Vero E6 cell viability was quantified with exposure of cells to lower drug doses, reflecting the 12-fold dilution of drugs when virus/drug mixture was incubated with cells

(n=3). The X-axes are scaled to log₁₀ - the lower X-axis refers to the concentration of drugs on the live virus and the upper X-axis refers to equivalent concentration of drugs on the cells. Percentage changes are with respect to no drug control which is set as 100%. IC₅₀ of the drugs is in mM and was determined using the non-linear regression fitting with a variable slope. Data are mean ± SD. **(F)** The effects of thiol drugs on Vero E6 cells during the two hours of SARS-CoV-2 infection as evaluated by addition of 8.3 mM or 0.52 mM of thiol drugs and SARS-CoV-2 simultaneously to the cell monolayer. These concentrations reflect the 12-fold dilution of drugs when virus/drug mixture was incubated with cells (n=3). Data are mean ± SD. **(G)** The effects of thiol drugs on Vero-TMPRSS2 cells during the two hours of SARS-CoV-2 infection as evaluated by addition of 6.25mM of thiol drugs and SARS-CoV-2 simultaneously to the cell monolayer. This concentration reflects the 24-fold dilution of drugs when virus/drug mixture was incubated with cells (corresponding to Fig. 3J, K) (n=3). Data are mean ± SD.

Figure S5.

Figure S5. Effect of pretreatment of cells with thiol drugs on entry of B.1.617 pseudoviruses and B.1.617.2 (Delta) authentic viruses. (A to F) Entry efficiency of B.1.617.1 and B.1.617.2 variant pseudoviruses, quantified by luciferase activity, when the HEK293T-ACE2-TMPRSS2 cells were exposed to (A) carbocysteine (sulfide drug, negative control) and thiol drugs (B) Mesna, (C) bucillamine, (D) TDG, (E) cysteamine (F) WR-1065 prior to transduction with untreated virus (as illustrated in Figure S2B), (n = 3-4). The X-axis are scaled to log₁₀. Percentage changes are with respect to no drug control which is set as 100%. Data are mean ± SD. **(G)** The effects of thiol drugs on Vero-TMPRSS2 cells during the two hours of SARS-CoV-2 infection as evaluated by addition of 6.25mM of thiol drugs and Delta SARS-CoV-2 simultaneously to the cell monolayer. This concentration reflects the highest concentration, post 24-fold dilution of drugs when

virus/drug mix was incubated with the cells in the virus pre-treatment experiment (n=3).
(corresponding to Figure 4 H-M). Data are mean \pm SD.

Figure S6.

Figure S6. Effect of pretreatment of either the pseudoviruses or HEK293T-ACE2-TMPRSS2 cells with cysteamine on entry of variant pseudoviruses. (A, B) Pseudovirus (PV) entry efficiency when the SARS-CoV-2 variant pseudoviruses were exposed to (A) carbocysteine (sulfide drug, negative control) and thiol drug (B) cysteamine prior to transduction into HEK293T-ACE2-TMPRSS2 cells (n = 3-4). The X-axis are scaled to log10. Percentage changes are with respect to no drug control which is set as 100%. Data are mean \pm SD. (C) IC50 values of cysteamine in the SARS-CoV-2

variant PV transduction assays. Data are mean \pm SEM. **(D, E)** Entry efficiency of the variant pseudoviruses, quantified by luciferase activity, when the cells were exposed to (D) carbocysteine and (E) cysteamine prior to transduction with untreated virus (n = 3-4). The X-axis are scaled to log₁₀. Percentage changes are with respect to no drug control which is set as 100%. Data are mean \pm SD.

Figure S7.

Figure S7. Effect of pretreatment of HEK293T-ACE2-TMPRSS2 cells with cysteine derivatives on B.1.617.1 pseudovirus entry. (A to C) Pseudovirus entry efficiency, quantified by luciferase activity, when the cells were exposed to cysteine derivatives (A) N-acetylcysteine, (B) L-cysteine, (C) L-cysteine methyl ester prior to transduction with untreated virus (n = 3-6). The X-axis are scaled to log₁₀. Percentage changes are with respect to no drug control which is set as 100%. Data are mean ± SD.

Figure S8

Figure S8. Effect of cysteamine on absolute lung weights of SARS-CoV-2 infected hamsters. Absolute lung weights in cysteamine treated and vehicle control groups. Control – intraperitoneal vehicle control group; CYS - cysteamine. Data are mean \pm SEM. Statistical significance was analyzed by two tailed, unpaired t-test between cysteamine treated (CYS) and respective control group (control).

Figure S9

Figure S8. Thiol drugs have broad antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. The antioxidant effects of thiol drugs relate to their ability to scavenge reactive oxygen species (ROS) and to replenish glutathione, either directly by increasing intracellular cysteine (NAC, cysteamine) or indirectly (bucillamine, tiopronin) (1–3). The anti-inflammatory effects of thiol drugs relate to their ability to a) interrupt ROS-mediated inflammatory cascades; b) decrease NF-κB activation and prevent downstream production of cytokines and chemokines; c) inhibit neutrophil-derived inflammatory mediators (4, 6, 8). In addition, cysteamine has specific anti-inflammatory effects related to its ability to inhibit transglutaminase 2 (TG2, a promoter of NF-κB-dependent cytokine secretion) (5, 7, 9) and somatostatin (limits substance P release and dampens neurogenic inflammation) (10).

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